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Title: Antifungal effect of engineered silver nanoparticles on phytopathogenic and toxigenic *Fusarium* spp. and their impact on mycotoxin accumulation

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Keywords: Silver nanoparticles; LC-MS/MS; *Fusarium* spp; fumonisins; trichothecenes; zearalenone

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Abstract: Cereal grains are essential ingredient in food, feed and industrial processing. One of the major causes of cereal spoilage and mycotoxin contamination is the presence of toxigenic *Fusarium* spp. Nanoparticles have immense applications in agriculture, nutrition, medicine or health but their possible impact on the management of toxigenic fungi and mycotoxins have been very little explored. In this report, the potential of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs), (size 14-100 nm) against the major toxigenic *Fusarium* spp. affecting crops and their effect on mycotoxin accumulation is evaluated for the first time. The studied *Fusarium* spp. (and associated mycotoxins) were *F. graminearum* and *F. culmorum* (deoxynivalenol, 3-acetyldeoxynivalenol and zearalenone), *F. sporotrichioides* and *F. langsethiae* (T-2 and HT-2 toxins), *F. poae* (nivalenol), *F. verticillioides* and *F. proliferatum* (fumonisins B1 and B2) and *F. oxysporum* (mycotoxins not detected). The factors fungal species, AgNP dose (range 2-45 µg/mL), exposure time (range 2-30 h) and their interactions significantly influence spore viability, lag period and growth rate (GR) in subsequent cultures in maize-based medium (MBM) of all the studied species. The effective lethal doses (ED50, ED90 and ED100) to control spore viability and GR were in the range 1- > 45 µg/mL depending on the remaining factors. At high exposure times (20-30 h), the three effective doses ranged 1-30 µg/mL for all the studied species. At the end of the incubation period (10 days) mycotoxin levels in MBM cultures inoculated with fungal spores from treatments were strongly related with the size reached by the colony at that time. None of the treatments produced stimulation in conidia germination, GR or mycotoxin biosynthesis with respect to controls. Thus, the antifungal effect of the assayed AgNPs against the tested *Fusarium* spp. suggests that AgNPs could be a new antifungal ingredient in bioactive polymers (paints, films or coating) likely to be implemented in the agro-food sector for controlling these important toxigenic *Fusarium* spp. and their main associated mycotoxins.

Highlights

- AgNPs (30 nm) showed a potent antifungal activity against toxigenic *Fusarium* spp
- AgNPs affected spore viability, and lag phase and growth rate of *Fusarium* colonies
- AgNPs caused a significant decrease in *Fusarium* mycotoxin accumulation
- AgNP treatments did not stimulate fungal growth or mycotoxin accumulation
- Effective AgNP doses (ED₅₀, ED₉₀, ED₁₀₀) depend on fungal species and exposure time

1 **Antifungal effect of engineered silver nanoparticles on phytopathogenic and**
2 **toxigenic *Fusarium* spp. and their impact on mycotoxin accumulation**

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19 **Abstract**

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21 major causes of cereal spoilage and mycotoxin contamination is the presence of toxigenic
22 *Fusarium* spp. Nanoparticles have immense applications in agriculture, nutrition, medicine
23 or health but their possible impact on the management of toxigenic fungi and mycotoxins
24 have been very little explored. In this report, the potential of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs),
25 (size 14-100 nm) against the major toxigenic *Fusarium* spp. affecting crops and their effect
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28 acetyldeoxynivalenol and zearalenone), *F. sporotrichioides* and *F. langsethiae* (T-2 and
29 HT-2 toxins), *F. poae* (nivalenol), *F. verticillioides* and *F. proliferatum* (fumonisins B₁ and
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33 based medium (MBM) of all the studied species. The effective lethal doses (ED₅₀, ED₉₀ and
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36 30 µg/mL for all the studied species. At the end of the incubation period (10 days)
37 mycotoxin levels in MBM cultures inoculated with fungal spores from treatments were
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40 controls. Thus, the antifungal effect of the assayed AgNPs against the tested *Fusarium*
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47

48 1. Introduction

49 Mycotoxins are secondary fungal metabolites mainly produced by toxigenic species
50 of *Fusarium*, *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium* and *Alternaria*. Infections of cereal grains by toxigenic
51 fungi result in severe reductions in crop yield, mycotoxin contamination and economical
52 losses thus limiting the marketability of grain supply worldwide (European Union, 2018).
53 For a long time, the Food and Agriculture Organization has estimated that approximately
54 25% of the cereal-based foods produced in the world are contaminated with mycotoxins
55 (FAO, 2004). Currently, this percentage could be higher due to climate change and to new
56 estimations of mycotoxin occurrence in cereals and by-products by rapid methods that
57 have become increasingly popular due to their high sample throughput and multi-analyte
58 capabilities (Ogara et al., 2017; Romera et al., 2018).

59 Although fungi can collectively produce hundreds of mycotoxins, only few of them
60 are subject to regulation and they are a serious global problem (Marasas, 2008). Most of
61 the regulated mycotoxins in cereals and their by-products are produced by *Fusarium* spp.
62 The distribution and growth of species belonging to the genus *Fusarium* and occurrence of
63 the associated mycotoxins are closely related to climate factors, such as temperature and
64 moisture (Desjardins, 2006; Xu et al., 2008), and their prevalence is consequently
65 expected to increase as a result of present and future climate change (Medina et al., 2017;
66 Moretti et al., 2019).

67 *Fusarium* head blight or scab in small-grain cereals (wheat, barley, oats, rye and
68 triticale) and stalk and ear rot in maize are devastating and recurrent diseases affecting
69 crops worldwide. They are caused by different *Fusarium* spp, especially, *F. graminearum*
70 and *F. culmorum* (Bottalico and Perrone, 2002; Logrieco et al., 2002; Parry et al., 1995)
71 and other phytopathogenic species, such as *F. oxysporum*, known to cause root rot in
72 more than 100 relevant plant species (Agrios, 2005). In addition, various mycotoxins can

73 accumulate in the seeds, among them, deoxynivalenol (DON), their 3- and 15-acetyl-
74 derivatives (3-AcDON and 15-AcDON) and zearalenone (ZEA) (Eckard et al., 2011;
75 Fredlund et al., 2013; Ogara et al., 2017; Oliveira et al., 2017). Generally, these fungi and
76 secondary metabolites are accompanied by other relevant fungal species and their major
77 mycotoxins. They are *F. sporotrichioides* and *F. langsethiae* and type-A trichothecenes,
78 including T-2 and HT-2 toxins (Fredlund et al., 2013; Mateo, et al., 2011; 2013; Thrane et
79 al., 2004), *F. poae* and nivalenol (NIV) (Martin et al., 2018; Thrane et al., 2004), *F.*
80 *verticillioides* and *F. proliferatum* and fumonisin B₁ (FB₁) and fumonisin B₂ (FB₂) (Cendoya
81 et al., 2018; Choi et al., 2018; Oliveira et al., 2017).

82 All these mycotoxins pose significant hazards to human and animal health but only
83 DON, ZEA and FB₁ + FB₂ are currently regulated in cereals and cereal derivatives in the
84 European Union (European Commission, 2006, 2007). For T-2 + HT-2, recommendations
85 about permissible levels have been published (European Commission, 2013). The
86 International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC, 1993) has classified DON, ZEA, FB₁
87 + FB₂, and T-2 + HT-2 into groups, 3, 3, 2B and 3, respectively. These mycotoxins are
88 compounds with nephrotoxic, hepatotoxic, immunosuppressive and mutagenic properties,
89 among others (Escrivá et al., 2015). Thus, prevention and control of these toxigenic
90 *Fusarium* spp. and mycotoxin biosynthesis are priority objectives in food security and food
91 safety.

92 Currently, there are several approaches to reduce these risks such as good
93 agricultural and manufacturing practices (Luo et al., 2018), biocontrol (Nguyen et al., 2017)
94 or the use of chemical antifungal agents (Mateo et al., 2011, 2013). However, the
95 problems associated with fungi and mycotoxins persist, and new and additional strategies
96 for an integrated management of toxigenic fungi in food and feed are required.

97 The rapid development of nanotechnology has transformed many domains of food
98 science, especially those that involve agricultural practices, processing, packaging,

99 storage, transportation, functionality and other safety aspects of food (Bajpai et al., 2018;
100 Duhan et al., 2017; Hamad et al., 2018; Hannon et al., 2015; Jo et al., 2015; King et al.,
101 2018; Mishra et al., 2014). In this context, metal nanoparticles (NPs) (Ag, Cu, Zn, Au, Ti...)
102 and metal-based composites (ZnO, SiO₂, TiO₂, TiN...), with antimicrobial properties are
103 used and exploited in the food industry to improve the properties of food packaging and
104 other active materials (Bumbudsanpharoke and Ko, 2015; Carbone et al., 2016; Hannon et
105 al., 2015). Among them, engineered silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) are currently the most
106 studied and the most effective against a wide range of bacteria, yeasts, molds and viruses
107 (Khezerlou et al., 2018; Rai et al., 2009). AgNPs exhibit low volatility and stability at high
108 temperatures, can be hosted in different matrices, polymers and stabilizing agents. They
109 show better antimicrobial properties than metallic silver due to their extremely large
110 surface area, which can provide a better contact with the microorganism (Carbone et al.,
111 2016; Hannon et al., 2015).

112 The main drawback of NPs in food technology is its possible migration from the
113 hosted polymer to the food, by contact. Therefore, this issue has been the focus of
114 considerable attention (Carbone et al., 2016; Souza et al., 2016; Störmer et al., 2017). For
115 silver, EFSA have provided upper limits for Ag migration (EFSA, 2011). Recommendations
116 are not to exceed 0.05 mg/L in water and 0.05 mg/kg in food. This implies that precise and
117 urgent estimations of the minimum effective doses of AgNPs to control growth of target
118 microorganisms in food are necessary. To date, very little research focused on the effect
119 of NPs on toxigenic fungi growth and mycotoxin production has been carried out (Abd-
120 Elsalam et al., 2017).

121 The aims of the present study were: i) to get effective engineered silver
122 nanoparticles (AgNPs) for controlling phytopathogenic and toxigenic *Fusarium* spp. and
123 mycotoxin production using AgNO₃, sodium borohydride and sodium citrate, and ii) to
124 evaluate the effect of the synthesized AgNPs on the growth of target fungal species and

125 on the biosynthesis of their main associated mycotoxins. The fungi and mycotoxins
126 included in the study were *F. graminearum* and *F. culmorum* (DON, 3–AcDON, and ZEA),
127 *F. sporotrichioides* and *F. langsethiae* (T–2 and HT–2), *F. poae* (NIV), *F. proliferatum* and
128 *F. verticillioides* (FB₁ and FB₂) and *F. oxysporum* (the used strain was previously assayed
129 did not produce any of the studied mycotoxins).

130 **2. Materials and Methods**

131 *2.1. Reagents and standards*

132 Silver nitrate (AgNO₃) (>99.9% pure), and standards of mycotoxins DON, 3–
133 AcDON, NIV, ZEA, FB₁, FB₂, T–2, and HT–2 were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich
134 (Alcobendas, Spain). Yeast extract was from Panreac (Montcada i Reixac, Barcelona,
135 Spain). Sodium borohydride (NaBH₄, >99% pure), trisodium citrate (TSC, 99% pure),
136 sodium hydroxide, ammonium formate and Tween 80 were from Merck (Darmstadt,
137 Germany). All reagents supplied were of analytical grade. Acetonitrile, formic acid, ethanol,
138 methanol (all LC grade) were from J.T. Baker (Deventer, the Netherlands). Pure water was
139 obtained from a Milli-Q Plus apparatus (Millipore, Billerica, MA, USA).

140 *2.2. Synthesis of AgNPs*

141 AgNPs were obtained according to the method reported by Agnihotri et al. (2014)
142 for synthesizing nanoparticles with a mean size of 30 nm. NaBH₄ was as used as a
143 primary reductant while TSC was both a secondary reductant and a stabilizing agent. The
144 reduction processes were carried out at two temperatures: 60 °C first and 90 °C
145 afterwards, mediated predominantly by NaBH₄ and TSC, respectively. One hundred and
146 eighty mL of 0.001M NaBH₄ and 0.0055 M TSC was heated at 60 °C for 30 min in the dark
147 under stirring. Afterwards, 20 mL of a 0.004 M solution of AgNO₃ was added drop wise.
148 The temperature was raised to 90 °C and the pH was set to 10.5 using 0.1 M solution of

149 NaOH. Heating proceeded for 20 min under continuous stirring. The AgNP suspension
150 was cooled at room temperature and was centrifuged (12000 x g, 20 min). The
151 supernatant was carefully removed to avoid taking the nanoparticles located on the bottom
152 and discarded. Then, the NPs were washed with pure water and centrifuged under the
153 same conditions six times to remove the unreacted reagents and most products of the
154 reaction (borate, excess citrate, ionic silver, etc.). Ionic silver was not detected in the
155 supernatant using the turbidity test with concentrated solution of NaCl. Finally, the AgNPs
156 were suspended in pure water and the pH was 6.6 ± 0.1 . The suspension was finally
157 stored at 4 °C when not in use. A small aliquot of fresh suspension was separated for
158 characterization.

159 *2.3. AgNP characterization*

160 *2.3.1. Characterization by single particle inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry* 161 *(SP-ICP-MS)*

162 The reagents used for SP-ICP-MS characterization were a certified standard of Ag
163 of 1000 mg/L (High-Purity Standards, Charleston, SC, USA) and a standard of gold
164 nanoparticles (50 nm diameter) and 3.51×10^{10} AuNPs/mL (Sigma-Aldrich). A standard of
165 1 mg Ag/L was prepared by dilution of the certified AgNP standard. Standards of AuNPs
166 (50 nm) were also prepared by successive dilution of the concentrate AuNP standard. The
167 original standard and all dilutions were sonicated for 10 min. The samples were prepared
168 as described for AuNP standards.

169 The conditions and parameters for ICP-MS characterization were: Instrument: ICP-
170 MS Agilent model 7900, with concentric nebulizer type Micromist, a Scott-type spray
171 camera, Pt-cone interphase, double lens off-axis, hyperbolic quadrupole as mass filter and
172 octopole collision/reaction cell using He and H₂, respectively. Plasma gas (Ar) flow rate
173 (L/min) 15; Auxiliary gas flow (L/min) 1.0; RF Power (W) 1550; RF Matching (V) 1.80;

174 Sampling depth (mm) 8.0; Nebulizer pump (rps) 0.1; Carrier gas (L/min) 1.07; Sample
175 uptake rate (mL/min) 0.35; Plasma mode: Low matrix; Spray chamber temperature (°C)
176 2.0; Integration parameters: Acquisition mode TRA (Time Resolved Analysis Mode);
177 Integration time/mass (ms) 3; Acquisition time (s) 60; Cell parameters: Isotope monitored
178 ¹⁰⁷Ag; Cell gas He; Cell gas flow (mL/min) 4.0; Energy discrimination (V) 2.0; Octopole RF
179 (V) 200.

180 2.3.2. Characterization by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

181 The suspension of AgNPs was examined by TEM to obtain the distribution of
182 nanoparticle sizes by a complementary method. A JEOL JEM-1010 (JEOL Co., Ltd.,
183 Tokyo, Japan) electron microscope of accelerating voltage 40 - 100 kV coupled to a digital
184 camera AMT RX80 (8 Mpx) was used. A drop of the AgNP suspension in pure water was
185 deposited onto a Formvar/carbon film 300-mesh copper grid. The solvent was allowed to
186 evaporate at room temperature.

187 2.4. Fungal strains and inocula preparation

188 Isolates of the species *F. graminearum* (Fg22), *F. culmorum* (Fc15), *F.*
189 *sporotrichioides* (Fs4), *F. langsethiae* (Fl021), *F. poae* (Fp11), *F. oxysporum* (Fo11), *F.*
190 *proliferatum* (Fp16) and *F. verticillioides* (Fv27) were previously isolated from cereals
191 grown in Spain except *F. langsethiae* that was isolated from oats grown in Germany
192 (Schleswig-Holstein region) and marketed in Spain. Identification of fungi was carried out
193 by conventional and PCR protocols following the methodology described by Gil-Serna et
194 al. (2013). All strains are held in the Mycology and Mycotoxins Group Culture Collection
195 (Valencia University, Spain). Before carrying out the study, the strains were grown in Yeast
196 Extract Sucrose (YES) medium (20 g agar, 20 g yeast extract, 150 g sucrose, 1 g
197 MgSO₄·7H₂O, 1000 mL water). The medium was autoclaved at 115 °C for 30 min and

198 poured into Petri dishes. The strains were inoculated on the center of the plates and
199 incubated at 28 °C for 7 days. Spores of these fresh cultures were used to prepare inocula
200 for further experiments on the efficacy of AgNPs to control fungal growth and mycotoxin
201 production.

202 *2.5. Impact of AgNPs on spore viability and colony growth*

203 *2.5.1. Preparation of culture medium*

204 To determine the effect of AgNPs on fungal growth, maize-based medium (MBM)
205 (3% w/v of milled maize grains + 2% w/v agar in pure water), a representative matrix
206 based on cereal was used (Tarazona et al., 2018). Previous analysis of maize grains
207 ensured they had undetectable mycotoxin levels. MBM was autoclaved in Erlenmeyer
208 flasks at 115 °C for 30 min. Water activity (a_w) level in the sterile medium was measured in
209 a flask control and adjusted in all flasks to 0.99 by addition of sterile glycerol/water using a
210 moisture adsorption curve for MBM previously determined. A RTD-502 unit (Novasina
211 GmbH, Pfäffikon, Switzerland) was used to perform all a_w measurements. Then, the
212 medium was poured into Petri dishes (25 mL/dish).

213 *2.5.2. Treatments*

214 Contact assays between fungal spores and AgNPs at different doses and exposure
215 times were carried out. To this purpose, tubes containing 5 mL of sterile pure water and
216 Tween 80 (0.005%) without AgNPs (controls) and tubes containing 5 mL of water and non-
217 ionic surfactant Tween 80 (0.005%) and supplemented with 2, 5, 10, 15, 30 and 45 μ g
218 AgNPs/mL (treatments) were prepared. Controls and AgNP suspensions were inoculated
219 with 1×10^5 spores/mL of fresh fungal cultures (7-day old) and vortexed for 30 s by a Stuart
220 vortex mixer. Controls and treatments were placed in an orbital shaker (Infors-HT
221 Aerotron, Bottmingen, Switzerland) at 60 rpm and 25 °C for 30 h. To evaluate the stability

222 of the suspension during the exposure period of the spores to AgNPs the spectrum of a
223 diluted suspension in water containing Tween 80 (0.005%) was recorded over a 30-h
224 period in a quartz cuvette (1.0 cm) from 300 to 800 nm. An Agilent 8453 diode array
225 spectrophotometer was used to this purpose.

226 2.5.3. Evaluation of individual spore viability after treatments

227 To assess the number of viable spores of the different fungal species in controls
228 and treatments, aliquots of 500 μ L (Section 2.5.2) were removed from test tubes at 0, 2, 4,
229 20 and 30 h of contact between spores and AgNPs and transferred to tubes containing 4.5
230 mL of sterile saline solution (9 g NaCl/L pure water). The diluted sample was vortexed for
231 30 s and used to prepare successive tenfold serial dilutions (10^{-2} – 10^{-5}) in sterile saline
232 solution. From each dilution, a 100- μ L aliquot was spread on the surface of MBM-
233 containing Petri dishes. Inoculated plates were incubated at 28 °C, except *F. langsethiae*
234 cultures, which were incubated at 25 °C (Mateo et al., 2011, 2013). Cultures were
235 incubated for 5 days in the dark, enclosed in sealed plastic containers together with
236 beakers of a glycerol–water solution matching the same a_w (0.99) to maintain a constant
237 equilibrium relative humidity inside the boxes. After the incubation period, fungal colony
238 forming units/mL (CFU/mL), effective doses to reduce the number of viable spores to 50%
239 (ED_{50}), 90% (ED_{90}) and 100 % (ED_{100}) or minimal lethal concentration (MLC) were
240 estimated by interpolation in the graphs of CFU/mL versus AgNP dose at each exposure
241 time. Three independent test were performed and they were repeated twice.

242 2.5.4. Evaluation of colony growth after treatments

243 For monitoring colony growth, 3- μ L aliquots of spore suspensions (control and
244 treatments) (Section 2.5.2) were removed just after 2, 4, 20 and 30 h of contact (fungal
245 spores-AgNPs) and centrally inoculated on the surface of MBM plates. Dishes were
246 incubated at 28 °C, except *F. langsethiae* (25 °C), in the dark for 10 days, enclosed in

247 sealed plastic containers together with beakers of a glycerol–water solution matching the
248 same a_w (0.99). The treatment effects (AgNP dose and exposure time) on colony lag
249 period and colony radial growth rate (GR) of the different species was determined in MBM
250 cultures. Lag phase was considered as the time (days) to reach a colony 5 mm diameter.
251 Then, two perpendicular colony diameters were daily measured with the help of a ruler and
252 a magnifying glass and the mean radius was calculated. Colony GR (mm/day) was
253 calculated in all cultures as the slope of the line obtained by linear regression of mean
254 radius vs time. The AgNP doses ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) necessary for 50%, 90%, and 100% growth
255 reduction (ED_{50} , ED_{90} and ED_{100}) in MBM were determined, when possible, by graphical
256 interpolation in the plots of GR vs AgNP dose in treatments. Three independent test were
257 performed and they were repeated twice.

258 *2.6. Determination of mycotoxins in MBM*

259 To determine the effect of AgNPs on mycotoxin production, at the end of incubation
260 period (10 days), the cultures in MBM used for GR evaluation were removed from Petri
261 dishes, homogenized and analyzed for DON, 3–AcDON, NIV, ZEA, FB_1 , FB_2 , T–2 and HT–
262 2 depending of the fungal species. For analysis, the UPLC–MS/MS method described by
263 Romera et al. (2018) was followed with minor modifications concerning differences in
264 matrix nature, the mycotoxins to be determined and their levels (as described in Sections
265 2.6.1, 2.6.2 and 2.6.3). Before determination of mycotoxin concentrations in MBM cultures,
266 calibration and validation assays were carried out.

267 *2.6.1. Calibration*

268 Solid mycotoxin standards were dissolved in acetonitrile to give stock concentrated
269 solutions. They were further diluted and added to extracts from non-inoculated (blank)
270 solid MBM to perform matrix-matched calibrations. Blank MBM were homogenized in

271 stomacher. Two g of the homogenate was mixed with 8 mL of acetonitrile/water/formic
272 acid (80:19:1, v/v/v) in a Falcon tube and shaken in orbital shaker for 60 min. The mixture
273 was centrifuged at 4260 x g for 5 min. Then, two mL of the supernatant was evaporated to
274 dryness under a slight stream of N₂. The residue was added with the appropriate volumes
275 of standards and then diluted (if necessary) with acetonitrile/water/formic acid (80:19:1,
276 v/v/v) up to a volume of 2.0 mL to attain the desired concentrations. Calibration standards
277 were filtered to injection vials using a syringe filter (0.22 µm, PTFE) and injected into the
278 UPLC–MS/MS system. For each mycotoxin, calibration lines were obtained by linear
279 regression (weighting by 1/x) of the peak areas from the quantifier ion vs concentration.
280 The concentration ranges (µg/mL) were DON (0.031–0.625); 3–AcDON (0.0125–0.250);
281 NIV (0.031–0.625); ZEA (0.0125–0.200); FB₁ (0.03–0.940); FB₂ (0.03–0.313); T–2 and
282 HT–2 (0.003–0.063).

283 2.6.2. *Mycotoxin recovery*

284 Method validation was carried out by analysis of blank MBM spiked with standards
285 of ZEA, DON, 3–AcDON, NIV, FB₁, FB₂, T–2 and HT–2 (n = 5) at different concentrations,
286 which was achieved by addition of aliquots of mycotoxin standard solutions to Erlenmeyer
287 flasks containing 10 g of autoclaved MBM allowed to cool to around 45 °C. The level range
288 (µg/g MBM) for recovery studies was 1.0–20.0 for DON, 0.1–0.80 for NIV, 1.0–3.0 for ZEA,
289 1.0–20.0 for 3–AcDON, 0.10–0.25 for T–2 and HT–2, 0.15–3.0 for FB₁, and 0.15–1.0 for
290 FB₂. Once homogenized, the spiked MBM was poured in Petri dishes and let to cool at
291 room temperature. After solvent evaporation, the solid medium was cut into small pieces
292 and was homogenized using a stomacher. The spiked homogenate (2.0 ± 0.1 g) was
293 extracted in a capped Falcon tube with 8 mL acetonitrile/water/formic acid (80:19:1, v/v/v)
294 in orbital shaker for 1 h. After centrifugation at 4260 x g, during 5 min, 2.0 mL of the
295 supernatant was filtered through 0.22–µm PTFE syringe filter for injection into the UPLC–

296 MS/MS system. Concentrations were determined by interpolation of the signals in the
297 calibrations lines (Section 2.6.1). Suitable dilution was necessary with high mycotoxin
298 concentrations to maintain them within the linear calibration range. Then, mean recovery
299 rates and their relative standard deviations were calculated.

300 *2.6.3. Determination of mycotoxins in MBM cultures*

301 At the end of the incubation period, the mycotoxins accumulated in MBM by the
302 *Fusarium* spp. strains were determined. The whole culture in Petri dishes (substrate plus
303 fungal biomass) was cut into small pieces, removed, weighed, homogenized in a
304 stomacher and analyzed as described in Section 2.6.2 for spiked media. Extracts filtered
305 using 0.22- μ m filters were injected into the UPLC–MS/MS system. When mycotoxin levels
306 in cultures were too high for the linear calibration range, extracts were appropriately diluted
307 with the same solvent and injected again. Concentrations were determined by interpolation
308 in the calibrations lines obtained with standards (Section 2.6.1).

309 *2.6.4. Instrumental conditions*

310 The UPLC–MS/MS system consisted of an ACQUITY UPLC™ system (Waters,
311 Manchester, UK), provided with an electrospray ionization interface (ESI). An ACQUITY
312 UPLC BEH C18 column (50 × 2.1 mm, 1.7 μ m particle size) (Waters) set at 25 °C was
313 used for separation. The injection volume was 30 μ L. The mobile phase was a time-
314 programmed mix of a) an aqueous buffer of formic acid (0.1%)/ammonium formate (0.15
315 mmol/L) and b) methanol. The flow-rate was 0.35 mL/min. MS/MS detection was
316 accomplished using an ACQUITY TQD tandem quadrupole mass spectrometer (Waters
317 Co., Milford, MA, USA). The ESI interface was used in positive ion mode (ESI+). A detailed
318 set of instrumental conditions are reported in Romera et al. (2018).

319 *2.7. Statistics*

320 Data were analyzed by multifactor analysis of variance (ANOVA) and linear
321 regression using Statgraphics Centurion XV.II statistical package (StatPoint, Inc., VA,
322 USA). *Post-hoc* Duncan's multiple range test ($\alpha = 0.05$) was used to find homogenous
323 groups when significant differences between factors were revealed by ANOVA. For
324 calculation purposes, undetectable mycotoxin levels were considered to be zero.

325 **3. Results and discussion**

326 *3.1. AgNP characterization*

327 The study of AgNP size distribution and concentration obtained by SP-ICP-MS
328 gave the following results: average size (30 nm), range (20–100 nm), number of
329 particles/mL (6.6×10^{10}) and silver concentration (60.26 mg/L). The minimum particle
330 diameter measured by using this technique was 20 nm due to sample background and the
331 dwell time utilized (1500 cps, 3 ms). The size distributions obtained by SP-ICP-MS and by
332 TEM appear in Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b, respectively. Overall, both agree although particles
333 with sizes < 20 nm could be observed using TEM. A sample micrograph obtained by TEM
334 for these AgNPs appears in Fig.1c. The mean diameter was 30 nm. Differences in the
335 level of nanoparticles with respect to the report of Agnihotri et al. (2014) may be due to
336 small differences in the rates of heating, stirring and AgNO₃ addition, way of pH
337 measurement or in centrifugation/washing steps.

338 The spectra of synthesized AgNPs in water containing Tween 80, medium used for
339 fungal spore treatment, recorded between 300 and 800 nm displayed a surface plasmon
340 resonance band with maximum absorbance at 405–409 nm and there were not substantial
341 differences among them from 0 to 30 hours. The absorbance at the maximum was
342 constant and there was not red shift. The synthesized AgNPs were practically stable in the
343 medium used for fungal spore treatment during the exposure time although some

344 agglomeration of AgNPs seems to occur because the spectrum line changed slightly in the
345 450–550 nm zone in spite of the stability expected, since Kvítek et al. (2008) and Li et al.
346 (2012) reported that Tween 80 aids to prevent AgNP de-stabilization. No turbidity that
347 could be attributed to ion Ag⁺ was apparent when an aliquot of treatments was centrifuged
348 and part of the supernatant was mixed with a concentrated solution of NaCl. Moreover,
349 continuous shaking assures homogeneity of the suspension during spore treatment.

350 3.2. Effectiveness of AgNP treatments on fungal growth

351 Some previous studies on the effect of AgNPs on the growth of phytopathogenic
352 fungi have been published but very little is known about the impact of AgNPs on the
353 growth of toxigenic fungi and, in the few cases where such impact was studied, the
354 methodologies used were very different. The present work focuses on the study of the
355 impact of AgNPs on the growth of the main toxigenic *Fusarium* spp. in food as well as on
356 the study of the effects of these nanoparticles in the production and accumulation of their
357 major associated mycotoxins in the substrate. A non-toxicogenic phytopathogenic *F.*
358 *oxysporum* strain was included in the study. In this report, treatments of spore
359 suspensions with different AgNP doses at different exposure times were carried out. After
360 treatments we assessed: a) spore viability level by monitoring the number of CFU/mL and
361 effective doses of AgNPs to reduce the number of viable spores to 50%, 90%, and 100%
362 (ED₅₀, ED₉₀ and ED₁₀₀ = MLC) as compared to untreated controls; b) colony development
363 of the exposed spore populations by monitoring of lag period, radial GR of the colonies
364 and effective doses of AgNPs to reduce GR to 50%, 90%, and 100% (ED₅₀, ED₉₀, and
365 ED₁₀₀ = MLC); and c) mycotoxin accumulation in MBM cultures inoculated with spores from
366 controls and treatments. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report where the
367 effect of AgNPs on these important parameters (spore viability, lag period, colony GR and
368 mycotoxin production) related to toxigenic *Fusarium* spp. is simultaneously studied

369 3.2.1. Effect of AgNPs on individual spore viability.

370 The combined effects of AgNP concentration and exposure time on conidia viability
371 of toxigenic *Fusarium* spp. appear in Fig. 2 and Table 1. Overall, a decrease in the number
372 of CFU/mL with increasing AgNP dose and contact time can be observed for all the
373 assayed species (Fig. 2). *F. poae* was the most sensitive species as treatments of 10 µg
374 AgNPs/mL for 2 h completely inhibited germination of the exposed spore population. By
375 the contrary, doses of 45 µg AgNPs/mL during > 4 h were required to achieve this result in
376 treatments of *F. culmorum*, *F. proliferatum*, *F. verticillioides* and *F. oxysporum* spores.
377 ANOVA showed that the factors fungal species, AgNP dose, exposure time and the three
378 possible two-way interactions between these factors significantly influence spore viability
379 ($p < 0.01$). With regard to AgNP concentration and exposure time, Duncan's test found
380 seven and four homogeneous non-overlapping groups, respectively (Table 2). However,
381 the eight species were grouped in three homogeneous groups. These groups, listed in the
382 order of increasing spore susceptibility (decreasing spore viability) to AgNPs, were 1) *F.*
383 *oxysporum*; 2) *F. culmorum*, *F. sporotrichioides*, *F. proliferatum*, and *F. verticillioides*; 3) *F.*
384 *graminearum*, *F. poae* and *F. langsethiae*. Multiple linear regression indicates that there is
385 a negative relationship with AgNP dose and exposure time and that the effect of both
386 factors can explain about 59% of the whole variance concerning spore viability among the
387 tested species.

388 The ED₅₀, ED₉₀, and ED₁₀₀ of AgNPs against fungal spores in each treatment and
389 in each species are listed in Table 1. The ED₅₀ values were estimated for all the species at
390 all exposure times (≤ 45 µg/mL). However, at exposure times of 2 and 4 h, in some cases,
391 the ED₉₀ and ED₁₀₀ values exceeded 45 µg/mL depending on the species. After 20 h
392 exposure time, the three effective doses could be estimated for all the species. Overall,
393 when the contact time between AgNPs and spores increased these doses decreased.

394 3.2.2. Effect of AgNPs on lag period and colony growth rate

395 The mean lag period values of fungal colonies growing in MBM inoculated with
396 spore populations from controls and treatments are shown in Fig. 3. For statistical
397 calculations, when fungal growth was not observed at the end of incubation time (10 days),
398 a lag-value of 10 days was arbitrarily assumed. The measurable lag phases ranged
399 between 0.7 and 5.1 days, depending on the species and the treatment. Mycelial growth
400 was not observed in cultures inoculated with spores previously exposed to $\geq 30 \mu\text{g}$
401 AgNPs/mL for ≥ 20 h, regardless of the species, except for *F. oxysporum*. The longest
402 measurable lag phase (5.1 days) was found in cultures of *F. langsethiae* inoculated with
403 spores treated with $10 \mu\text{g}$ AgNPs/mL during 4 h. Spores treated with $10 \mu\text{g}$ AgNPs/mL
404 during 4 h produced undefined lag periods (> 10 days) in *F. poae* and *F. graminearum*
405 cultures. Fig. 4 shows the colony GR of the assayed species on MBM vs the AgNP dose
406 applied in treatments. The ED₅₀, ED₉₀, and ED₁₀₀ regarding GR (Table 3) were estimated
407 by graphical interpolation in the graphs displayed in Fig. 4. In short-time treatments (2–4
408 h), no ED could be estimated for *F. culmorum*, *F. proliferatum*, *F. oxysporum*, and *F.*
409 *verticillioides* (all exceeded $45 \mu\text{g/mL}$). However, at 20–30 h of exposure these parameters
410 could be estimated for all the assayed species. At these exposure times, the most
411 susceptible and the most resistant fungi were *F. langsethiae* and *F. oxysporum*,
412 respectively (Table 3).

413 ANOVA showed that AgNP dose, exposure time, fungal species and all the two-
414 way interactions significantly influenced ($p < 0.01$) the lag period and GR. Arrangement of
415 the three main factors into homogeneous groups according to Duncan's test ($\alpha = 0.05$)
416 appears in Table 2. Overall, there was a moderate negative correlation between GR and
417 the lag period and between the lag period and the number of viable spores in inocula after
418 AgNP treatments, which seems logical considering that high AgNP doses significantly
419 decrease the number of viable spores in inocula (Table 2). Such high doses could produce

420 alterations in the viable spores surviving the treatments, although this last hypothesis was
421 not confirmed. Regarding lag-phase duration and GR, Duncan's test grouped all AgNP
422 doses into five and four homogeneous non-overlapping groups, respectively. The fungal
423 species were clustered into five homogeneous groups. Concerning the lag phase the
424 fastest growing group was formed by *F. culmorum*, *F. verticillioides*, and *F. proliferatum*
425 and the slowest growing mold was *F. poae* while there was one homogeneous group for
426 each exposure time (Table 2).

427 Although lack of previous data makes comparative analysis difficult, some general
428 conclusions can be drawn. The available results suggest that the susceptibility of
429 phytopathogenic and/or toxigenic fungi to AgNPs depends on the size and species. Thus,
430 it has been reported that smaller and well-dispersed AgNPs increase the reactive surface
431 area increasing antimicrobial activity with respect to the larger ones (Hannon et al., 2015;
432 Xiu et al., 2012). This is probably due to the high intensity at which the AgNPs are capable
433 to saturate and adhere to the fungal hyphae and conidia. Bahrami-Teimoori et al. (2015)
434 found that minimal inhibitory concentrations of AgNPs (10–32 nm in diameter) to control
435 50% of mycelial growth of *Macrophomina phaseolina*, *Alternaria alternata*, *Fusarium*
436 *oxysporum*, *Trichoderma harzianum* and *Geotrichum candidum* in solid medium were
437 159.80, 337.09, 328.05, 400 and 400 µg/mL, respectively. Jo et al. (2015) showed that
438 AgNPs (approx. 7.5 nm in diameter) reduce viability of *Gibberella fujikuroi* conidia by 50%
439 when directly exposed to concentrations ranging from 0.015 to 1.5 µg/mL for 1 to 20 min,
440 and that doses of 150 µg/mL, for 10 min and up to 24 h, significantly decreased colony
441 forming units (CFU) of *G. fujikuroi* on rice seed. In addition, these authors found that seed
442 treatment with 150 µg AgNPs/mL for 12 or 24 h significantly improved seedling emergence
443 and height of *G. fujikuroi*-infested seeds. Adverse effects on germination rate and seedling
444 growth were not observed with any of the AgNP treatments (≤150 µg/mL for up to 48 h
445 exposure) tested in the study. Elgorban et al. (2016) examined the inhibition effect of

446 AgNPs (40–60 nm in diameter) in cultures of *Rhizoctonia solani* anastomosis groups
447 (AGs) infecting cotton plants and found that the ED₅₀ and ED₉₀ of AgNPs in two solid
448 cultures media ranged between 0.0002 and 0.0022 mol/L and between 0.0061 and 0.0671
449 mol/L, respectively. Kasprowicz et al. (2010) studied the impact of AgNPs on plant
450 pathogenic spores of *F. culmorum* reporting a significant reduction in mycelial growth after
451 a previous incubation of fungal spores with AgNPs (5–65 nm in diameter) at levels 0.12–
452 10 ppm for 2–24 h. The antifungal effect of AgNPs was dependent on the exposure time.
453 Suspensions of *F. culmorum* spores incubated with 2.5 ppm of AgNPs for 24 h had a
454 significantly lower percentage of germinating spores compared to the control. Dananjaya
455 et al. (2017) found that doses of 100 µg/mL of chitosan silver nanocomposites (373 nm
456 size) were effective (CMI) to inhibit growth of *F. oxysporum* species complex, and caused
457 morphological and ultrastructural negative changes in the pathogen, suggesting its usage
458 as an antifungal agent.

459 The size of the AgNPs seems to be decisive in their possible transfer and
460 application in the agri-food sector. In cytotoxicity assays measuring membrane damage
461 with human lung cells, 20 and 50 µg/mL of AgNPs (10 nm in diameter), independent of the
462 surface coating (citrate and polyvinylpyrrolidone), were toxic, whereas 40 and 75 nm NPs
463 were not (Gliga et al., 2014). Although the mass concentration (mg/mL) was the same, 10
464 nm AgNPs have surface areas and particle concentrations (number/mL) that are over 10-
465 and 1,000-times larger than those of 100 nm AgNPs, respectively, which may increase the
466 chance of interaction with surrounding biomolecules and trigger adverse responses (Cho
467 et al., 2018). Similarly, Park et al. (2011) found that 4 nm AgNPs induce much higher
468 levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS) production and interleukin-8 secretion from
469 macrophage immune cells than 20 and 70 nm AgNPs, suggesting that particle size may be
470 the main factor affecting AgNP toxicity. Silver in food additive E 174 is present in its
471 elemental form (silver-colored powder or tiny sheets). In the EU, specifications for silver

472 have been defined (European Commission, 2012). According to the Panel,
473 characterization of the particle size in the powder of E 174 should be included in the
474 specifications.

475 In our study, the eight *Fusarium* spp were grouped in three homogeneous groups
476 according to their spore susceptibility to AgNPs and it was possible to determine the ED₅₀,
477 ED₉₀, and ED₁₀₀ for all of them using AgNPs with an average size of 30 nm (range 14–100
478 nm by TEM) at doses of 2–45 µg/mL and exposure times in the range 2–30 h in liquid
479 medium. In general, AgNP effectiveness increased with increasing dose, regardless of the
480 fungal species. These results are in agreement with those obtained by the authors cited
481 above and those reported by other researchers (Jo et al., 2009; Kim et al., 2009; Min et al.,
482 2009; Park et al., 2006) concerning the control of different phytopathogenic fungal species.

483 3.3. Effect of AgNP treatments on mycotoxin production in MBM cultures

484 The method used for determination of the mycotoxins produced in MBM cultures
485 using UPLC-MS/MS was validated on the basis of recovery percentages and their relative
486 standard deviations (RSD). In the tested ranges (Section 2.6.2), mean recoveries and
487 their RSD for the different mycotoxins were as follows: DON (97% ± 5 %), NIV (97% ±
488 6%), ZEA (98% ± 6%), 3–AcDON (94% ± 7%), T–2 (99% ± 7%), HT–2 (96% ± 8%), FB₁
489 (102% ± 5%), and FB₂ (98% ± 6%). Some sample extracts had to be diluted because
490 mycotoxin levels were too high for the linear calibration ranges. The limits of detection
491 (LOD) (µg/mL) estimated as 3 × ratio signal/noise, were as follows: DON (0.02); NIV
492 (0.02); ZEA (0.005), 3–AcDON (0.012), T–2 (0.002), HT–2 (0.002), FB₁ (0.015), and FB₂
493 (0.015). The limits of quantification (LOQ) were estimated as 3.3 times the above LOD
494 values.

495 In general, mycotoxin levels in MBM cultures decreased when both AgNP dose
496 and contact period increased (Figs. 5–7). Mycotoxin levels at the end of the incubation

497 period (ten days) were closely correlated with the radius reached by the colony at that
498 time. Fig. 5 shows the mycotoxin levels in cultures of *F. graminearum* and *F. culmorum*
499 inoculated with spores previously treated (DON, 3–AcDON and ZEA). Toxins were
500 undetectable in most cultures at AgNP doses > 10 µg/mL and 20–30 h of exposure, which
501 was associated to lack of fungal growth. Fig. 6 shows the concentrations of T–2 and HT–2
502 in cultures of *F. sporotrichioides* and *F. langsethiae* and the levels of NIV in cultures of *F.*
503 *poae* at the 10th incubation day. Doses ≥ 15 µg/mL combined with exposure times ≥ 4 h
504 inhibited T–2 and HT–2 production. Fig. 7 displays the concentrations of FB₁ and FB₂ in
505 the cultures of *F. proliferatum* and *F. verticillioides*.

506 ANOVA found that AgNP dose and exposure time significantly influence ($p <$
507 0.005) the concentrations of DON, 3-AcDON and ZEA in the cultures of *F. graminearum*
508 and *F. culmorum*. The strains of both species gave statistically comparable DON levels.
509 However, *F. graminearum* produced significantly more 3–AcDON but less ZEA than *F.*
510 *culmorum* produced. Table 4 shows the arrangement of homogeneous groups devised by
511 the Duncan's multiple range test concerning mycotoxin levels. Concerning dose there
512 were four homogeneous overlapping groups for DON and 3–AcDON and five for ZEA.
513 With regard to exposure time, there were three, two and four homogeneous groups for
514 DON, 3–AcDON, and ZEA, respectively.

515 ANOVA found that AgNP dose, exposure and species significantly influence the
516 concentrations of T-2 and HT-2 in cultures of *F. sporotrichioides* and *F. langsethiae*. ($p <$
517 0.001). The two-way interactions between the factors species, AgNP dose and exposure
518 time was also significant ($p < 0.05$). The Duncan's test clustered the AgNP doses (0–45
519 µg/mL) into five and four homogeneous groups for T–2 and HT–2, respectively, and the
520 contact period in three homogenous groups (Table 4). In *F. poae* cultures, the AgNP dose
521 significantly influenced the NIV levels but, although such levels decreased with exposure
522 time, this factor was not significant. Fumonisin levels were significantly affected ($p <$

523 0.001) by AgNP dose and contact time and *F. proliferatum* produced significantly more
524 fumonisins than *F. verticillioides*. AgNP doses $\geq 30 \mu\text{g/mL}$ applied during ≥ 20 h were
525 effective to inhibit fumonisin production. Duncan's arrangements of homogeneous groups
526 for both fumonisins appear in Table 4.

527 According to our knowledge, there are no previous available data on the effect of
528 AgNPs in the production of mycotoxins by toxigenic *Fusarium* spp. Some researchers
529 have reported that AgNPs doses of 50–150 ppm can inhibit aflatoxin B₁ production at
530 levels of 46.1–100% (Al-Othman et al., 2014; Mousavi and Pourtalebi, 2015). The partial
531 or total inhibition of aflatoxin B₁ production in cultures was a direct consequence of the
532 AgNP effect on fungal growth. This conclusion agrees with the data found in our study for
533 the *Fusarium* spp. and mycotoxins studied.

534 In summary, the results obtained in the present study permit to extract general and
535 important conclusions. The factors fungal species, AgNP dose, exposure time and their
536 interactions significantly influence spore viability, lag period and growth rate of *F.*
537 *graminearum* (Fg22), *F. culmorum* (Fc15), *F. sporotrichioides* (Fs4), *F. langsethiae*
538 (FI021), *F. poae* (Fp11), *F. oxysporum* (Fo11), *F. proliferatum* (Fp16) and *F. verticillioides*
539 (Fv27). It is important to note that under the assayed conditions the ED₅₀, ED₉₀ and ED₁₀₀
540 for all fungal species were estimated using AgNPs of an acceptable size (average 30 nm,
541 range 14–100 nm by TEM) and within an acceptable concentration range (2–45 $\mu\text{g/mL}$).
542 The mycotoxin levels in the cultures inoculated with fungal spores from treatments at the
543 end of the incubation period were strongly related with the diameter reached by the colony
544 at that time. Obviously, the colony size depended on the number of viable spores in the
545 inoculum, lag period and mycelial GR. None of the tested treatments produced stimulation
546 of fungal growth or stimulation of mycotoxin biosynthesis with respect to controls. Thus,
547 the antifungal effect of assayed AgNPs against the tested *Fusarium* spp. suggests that
548 AgNPs could be a new antifungal ingredient likely to be implemented in the agro-food

549 sector for management of these important toxigenic fungi and their main associated
550 mycotoxins. In order to find effective concentrations of AgNPs in high-risk foods and
551 strategies to block excessive migration of nanoparticles to food (cleaning solutions,
552 paints, films...), further research will be necessary to perform in the future.

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557 **References**

- 558 Abd-Elsalam, K.A., Hashim, A.F., Alghuthaymi, M.A., Said-Galiev, E., 2017.
559 Nanobiotechnological strategies for toxigenic fungi and mycotoxins (Chapter 10). In:
560 Grumezescu, A.M. (Ed.), Food Preservation. Nanotechnology in the Agri-Food Industry.
561 Vol. 6. Academic Press, pp. 337–364.
- 562 Agnihotri, S., Mukherji, S., Mukherji, S., 2014. Size-controlled silver nanoparticles
563 synthesized over the range 5–100 nm using the same protocol and their antibacterial
564 efficacy. RSC Advances 4, 3974–3983.
- 565 Agrios, G.N., 2005. Plant Pathology, 5th Ed. Elsevier, Burlington, pp. 724–820.
- 566 Al-Othman, M.R., Abd El-aziz, A.R.M., Mahmoud, M.A., Eifan, S.A., El-shikh, M.S.,
567 Majrashi, M., 2014. Application of silver nanoparticles as antifungal and antiaflatoxin B1
568 produced by *Aspergillus flavus*. Dig. J. Nanomater. Biostruct. 9, 151–157.
- 569 Bahrami-Teimoori, B., Nikparast, Y., Hojatianfar, M., Akhlaghi, M., Ghorbani, R.,
570 Pourianfar, H.R., 2017. Characterisation and antifungal activity of silver nanoparticles

571 biologically synthesised by *Amaranthus retroflexus* leaf extract. J. Exp. Nanosci. 12,
572 129–139. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17458080.2017.1279355>.

573 Bajpai, V.K., Kamle, M., Shukla, S., Mahato, D.K., Chandra, P., Hwang, S.K., Kumar, P.,
574 Huh Y.S., Han, Y.K., 2018. Prospects of using nanotechnology for food preservation,
575 safety, and security. J. Food Drug Anal. 26, 1201–1214. DOI:
576 10.1016/j.jfda.2018.06.011.

577 Bottalico, A., Perrone, G., 2002. Toxigenic *Fusarium* species and mycotoxins associated
578 with head blight in small-grain cereals in Europe. Eur. J. Plant Pathol. 108, 611–624.

579 Bumbudsanpharoke, N., Ko, S., 2015. Nano-food packaging: an overview of market,
580 migration research and safety regulations. J. Food Sci. 80, R910–R923.

581 Carbone, M., Donia, D.T., Sabbatella, G., Antiochia, R., 2016. Silver nanoparticles in
582 polymeric matrices for fresh food packaging. J. King Saud. Univ. Sci. 28, 273–279.

583 Cendoya, E., Chiotta, M.L., Zachetti, V., Chulze, S.N., Ramirez, M.L., 2018. Fumonisin
584 and fumonisin-producing *Fusarium* occurrence in wheat and wheat by products: A
585 review. J. Cereal Sci. 80, 158–166.

586 Cho, Y.M., Mizuta, Y., Akagi, J.I., Toyoda, T., Sone, M., Ogawa K., 2018. Size-dependent
587 acute toxicity of silver nanoparticles in mice. J. Toxicol. Pathol. 31, 73–80.

588 Choi, J.H., Lee, S., Nah, J.Y., Kim, H.K., Paek, J.S., Lee. S., Ham, H., Hong, S.K., Yun,
589 S.H., Lee. T., 2018. Species composition and fumonisin production by the *Fusarium*
590 *fujikuroi* species complex isolated from Korean cereals. Int. J. Food Microbiol. 267, 62–
591 69.

592 Dananjaya, S.H.S., Erandani, W.K.C.U., Kim, C.H., Nikapitiya, C., Lee, J., De Zoysa, M.,
593 2017. Comparative study on antifungal activities of chitosan nanoparticles and chitosan

594 silver nano composites against *Fusarium oxysporum* species complex. Int. J. Biol.
595 Macromol. 105, 478–488.

596 Desjardins, A.E., 2006. *Fusarium* mycotoxins: Chemistry, Genetics and Biology. APS
597 Press. St. Paul, Minnesota, USA.

598 Duhan, J.S., Kumar, R., Kumar, N., Kaur, P., Nehra, K., Duhan, S., 2017. Nanotechnology:
599 The new perspective in precision agriculture. Biotechnol. Rep. (Amst.) 15, 11–23.

600 Eckard, S., Wettstein, F.E., Forrer, H.R., Vogelgsang, S., 2011. Incidence of *Fusarium*
601 species and mycotoxins in silage maize. Toxins 3, 949–967.

602 EFSA, European Food Safety Authority, 2011. Guidance on the risk assessment of the
603 application of nanoscience and nanotechnology in the food and feed chain. EFSA J. 9
604 (5), 2140.

605 Elgorban, A.M., El-Samawaty, A.E.M., Yassin, M.A., Sayed, S.R., Adil, S.F., Elhindi, K.M.,
606 Bakri, M., Khan, M., 2016. Antifungal silver nanoparticles: synthesis, characterization
607 and biological evaluation. Biotechnol. Equip. 30, 56–62,
608 DOI:10.1080/13102818.2015.1106339.

609 Escrivá, L., Font, G., Manyes, L., 2015. *In vivo* toxicity studies of *Fusarium* mycotoxins in
610 the last decade: A review. Food Chem. Toxicol. 78, 185–206.

611 European Commission, 2006. Commission Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 of 19
612 December 2006 setting maximum levels for certain contaminants in foodstuffs. Off. J.
613 Eur. Union L 364, 5–24.

614 European Commission, 2007. Commission Regulation (EC) 1126/2007 of 28 September
615 2007 amending Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 setting maximum levels for certain
616 contaminants in foodstuffs as regards *Fusarium* toxins in maize and maize products.
617 Off. J. Eur. Union L 255, 14–17.

618 European Commission, 2012. Commission Regulation (EC) 231/2012 of 9 March 2012
619 laying down specifications for food additives listed in Annexes II and III to Regulation
620 (EC) No 1333/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council. Off. J. Eur. Union L
621 83, 1–286.

622 European Commission, 2013. Commission Recommendation of 27 March 2013 on the
623 presence of T-2 and HT-2 toxin in cereals and cereal products (2013/165/EU). Off. J.
624 Eur. Union L91, 12–15.

625 European Union, 2018. RASFF (Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed). Annual reports
626 2002–2017. https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/rasff/reports_publications_en.

627 FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization), 2004. Worldwide regulations for mycotoxins in
628 foods and feeds in 2003. FAO Food and Nutrition Paper 81, Rome, Italy.

629 Fredlund, E., Gidlund, A., Sulyok, M., Börjesson, T., Krska, R., Olsen, M., Lindblad, M.,
630 2013. Deoxynivalenol and other selected *Fusarium* toxins in Swedish oats —
631 Occurrence and correlation to specific *Fusarium* species. Int. J. Food Microbiol. 167,
632 276–283.

633 Gil-Serna, J., Mateo, E.M., González-Jaén, M.T., Jiménez, M., Vázquez, C., Patiño, B.,
634 2013. Contamination of barley seeds with *Fusarium* species and their toxins in Spain:
635 an integrated approach. Food Addit. Contam. Part A 30, 372–380.

636 Gliga, A.R., Skoglund, S., Wallinder, I.O., Fadeel, B., Karlsson, H.L., 2014. Size-
637 dependent cytotoxicity of silver nanoparticles in human lung cells: the role of cellular
638 uptake, agglomeration and Ag release. Part. Fibre Toxicol. 11, 11.

639 Hamad, A.F., Han, J.H., Kim, B.C., Rather, I.A., 2018. Review. The intertwine of
640 nanotechnology with the food industry. Saudi J. Biol. Sci. 25, 27–30.

641 Hannon, J.C., Kerry, J., Cruz-Romero, M., Morris, M., Cummins, E., 2015. Advances and
642 challenges for the use of engineered nanoparticles in food contact materials. Trends
643 Food Sci. Technol. 43, 43–62.

644 IARC (International Agency for Research on Cancer), 1993. Some naturally occurring
645 substances: food items and constituents, heterocyclic aromatic amines and mycotoxins.
646 Monographs on the evaluation of carcinogenic risks to humans. Vol 56. Lyon, France.

647 Jo, Y.K., Byung, H.K., Geunhwa, J., 2009. Antifungal activity of silver ions and
648 nanoparticles on phytopathogenic fungi. Plant Dis. 10, 1037–1043.

649 Jo, Y.K., Cromwell, W., Jeong, H.K. Thorkelson, J., Roh, J.H., Shin, D.B., 2015. Use of
650 silver nanoparticles for managing *Gibberella fujikuroi* on rice seedlings. Crop Prot. 74,
651 65–69.

652 Khezerlou, A., Alizadeh-Sani, M., Azizi-Lalabadi, M., Ehsani, A., 2018. Nanoparticles and
653 their antimicrobial properties against pathogens including bacteria, fungi, parasites and
654 viruses. Microb. Pathog. 123, 505–526.

655 Kasprowicz, M.J., Koziół, M., Gorczyca, A., 2010. The effect of silver nanoparticles on
656 phytopathogenic spores of *Fusarium culmorum*. Can. J. Microbiol. 56, 247–253.

657 Kim, S.W., Kim, K.S., Lamsal, K., Kim, Y.J., Kim, S.B., Jung, M., Sim, S.J., Kim, H.S.,
658 Chang, S.J., Kim, J.K., Lee, Y.S., 2009. An in vitro study of the antifungal effect of silver
659 nanoparticles on oak wilt pathogen *Raffaelea* sp. J. Microbiol. Biotechnol. 19, 760–764.

660 King, T., Osmond-McLeod, M.J., Duffy, L.L., 2018. Nanotechnology in the food sector and
661 potential applications for the poultry industry. Trends Food Sci. Technol. 72, 62–73.

662 Kvítek, L., Panáček, A., Soukupová, J., Kolař, M., Večeřová, R., Pucek, R., Holecová, M.,
663 Zboril, R. 2008. Effect of surfactants and polymers on stability and antibacterial activity
664 of silver nanoparticles (NPs). J. Phys. Chem. C 112, 5825–5834.

665 Li, H.J., Zhang, A.Q., Hu, Y., Sui, L., Qian, D.J., Chen, M. 2012. Large scale synthesis and
666 self-organization of silver nanoparticles with Tween 80 as a reductant and stabilizer.
667 *Nanoscal. Res. Lett.* 7, 612–625.

668 Logrieco, A., Mulè, G., Moretti, A., Bottalico, A., 2002. Toxigenic *Fusarium* species and
669 mycotoxins associated with maize ear rot in Europe. *Eur. J. Plant Pathol.* 108, 597–
670 609.

671 Luo, Y., Liu, X., Li, J., 2018. Updating techniques on controlling mycotoxins - A review.
672 *Food Control* 89, 123–132.

673 Marasas, W.F.O., Gelderblom, W.C.A., Vismer, H.F., 2008. Mycotoxins: a global problem.
674 In: Leslie, J.F., Bandyopadhyay, R., Visconti, A. (Eds.), *Mycotoxins*. CABI,
675 Oxfordshire, UK, pp. 29–40.

676 Martin, C., Schöneberg, T., Vogelgsang, S., Mendes Ferreira, C.S., Morisoli, R., Bertossa,
677 M., Bucheli, T.D., Mauch-Mani, B., Mascher, F., 2018. Responses of oat grains to
678 *Fusarium poae* and *F. langsethiae* infections and mycotoxin contaminations. *Toxins*
679 10, 47. DOI:10.3390/toxins10010047.

680 Mateo, E.M., Valle-Algarra, F.M., Mateo-Castro, R., Jiménez, M., Magan, N., 2011. Effect
681 of fenpropimorph, prochloraz and tebuconazole on growth and production of T-2 and
682 HT-2 toxins by *Fusarium langsethiae* in oat-based medium. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 151,
683 289–298.

684 Mateo, E.M., Valle-Algarra, F.M., Jiménez, M., Magan, N., 2013. Impact of three sterol-
685 biosynthesis inhibitors on growth of *Fusarium langsethiae* and on T-2 and HT-2 toxin
686 production in oat grain under different ecological conditions. *Food Control* 34, 521–
687 529.

688 Medina, A., González-Jartin, J.M., Sainz, M.J., 2017. Impact of global warming on
689 mycotoxins. *Curr. Opin. Food Sci.* 18, 76–81.

690 Min, J.S., Kim, K.S., Kim, S.W., Jung, J.H., Lamsal, K., Kim, S.B., Jung, M.Y., Lee, Y.S.,
691 2009. Effects of colloidal silver nanoparticles on sclerotium-forming phytopathogenic
692 fungi. *Plant Pathol. J.* 25, 376–380.

693 Mishra, S., Singh, B.R., Singh, A., Keswani, C., Naqvi, A.H., Singh, H.B., 2014.
694 Biofabricated silver nanoparticles act as a strong fungicide against *Bipolaris*
695 *sorokiniana* causing spot blotch disease in wheat. *PLoS One*, 9, e97881,
696 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0097881>.

697 Moretti, A., Pascale, M.A., Logrieco, A.F., 2019. Mycotoxin risks under a climate change
698 scenario in Europe. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 84, 38–40.
699 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2018.03.008>.

700 Mousavi, S.A.A., Pourtalebi, S., 2015. Inhibitory effects of silver nanoparticles on growth
701 and aflatoxin B1 production by *Aspergillus parasiticus*. *Iranian J. Med. Sci.* 40, 501–
702 506.

703 Nguyen, P.A., Strub, C., Fontana, A., Schorr-Galindo, S., 2017. Crop molds and
704 mycotoxins: Alternative management using biocontrol. *Biol. Control* 104, 10–27.

705 Ogara, I.M., Zarafi, A.B., Alabi, O., Banwo, O., Ezekiel, C.N., Warth, B., Sulyok, M., Krska,
706 R., 2017. Mycotoxin patterns in ear rot infected maize: A comprehensive case study in
707 Nigeria. *Food Control* 73, 1159–1168.

708 Oliveira, M.S., Rocha, A., Sulyok, M., Krska, R., Mallmann, C.A., 2017. Natural mycotoxin
709 contamination of maize (*Zea mays* L.) in the South region of Brazil. *Food Control* 73,
710 127–132.

711 Park, H.J., Kim, S.H., Kim, H.J., Choi, S.H., 2006. A new composition of nanosized silica-
712 silver for control of various plant diseases. *Plant Pathol. J.* 22, 295–302.

713 Park, J., Lim, D.H., Lim, H.J., Kwon, T., Choi, J.S., Jeong, S., Choi, I.H., Cheon, J., 2011.
714 Size dependent macrophage responses and toxicological effects of Ag nanoparticles.
715 *Chem. Commun. (Camb)*. 47, 4382–4384.

716 Parry, D.W., Jenkinson, P., Mcleod, L., 1995. *Fusarium* ear blight (scab) in small-grain
717 cereals – a review. *Plant Pathol.* 44, 207–238.

718 Rai, M., Yadav, A., Gade, A., 2009. Silver nanoparticles as a new generation of
719 antimicrobials. *Biotechnol. Adv.* 27, 76–83.

720 Romera, D., Mateo, E.M., Mateo-Castro, R., Gómez, J.V., Gimeno-Adelantado, J.V.,
721 Jiménez, M., 2018. Determination of multiple mycotoxins in feedstuffs by combined
722 use of UPLC–MS/MS and UPLC–QTOF–MS. *Food Chem.* 267, 140–148.

723 Souza, V.G.L., Fernando, A.L., 2016. Nanoparticles in food packaging: Biodegradability
724 and potential migration to food—A review. *Food Pack. Shelf Life* 8, 63–70.

725 Störmer, A., Bott, J., Kemmer, D., Franz, R., 2017. Critical review of the migration potential
726 of nanoparticles in food contact plastics. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 63, 39–50.

727 Tarazona, A., Gómez, J.V., Gavara, R., Mateo-Castro, R., Gimeno-Adelantado, J.V.,
728 Jiménez, M., Mateo, E.M., 2018. Risk management of ochratoxigenic fungi and
729 ochratoxin A in maize grains by bioactive EVOH films containing individual
730 components of some essential oils. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 269, 107–119.

731 Thrane, U., Adler, A., Clasen, P.E., Galvano, F., Langseth, W., Lew, H., Logrieco, A.,
732 Nielsen, K.F., Ritieni, A., 2004. Diversity in metabolite production by *Fusarium*
733 *langsethiae*, *Fusarium poae*, and *Fusarium sporotrichioides*. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 95,
734 257–266.

735 Xiu, Z.M., Zhang, Q.B., Puppala, H.L., Colvin, V.L., Alvarez, P.J.J., 2012. Negligible
736 particle-specific antibacterial activity of silver nanoparticles. *Nano Lett.* 12,
737 4271e4275.

738 Xu, X.M., Nicholson, P., Thomsett, M.A., Simpson, D., Cooke, B.M., Doohan, F.M.,
739 Brennan, J., Monaghan, S., Moretti, A., Mulè, G., Hornok, L., Beki, E., Tatnell, J.,
740 Ritieni, A., Edwards, S.G., 2008. Relationship between the fungal complex causing
741 *Fusarium* head blight in wheat and environmental conditions. *Phytopathology* 98, 69–
742 78.

743

744 **Figure captions**

745 Fig. 1. (a) Histogram showing the distribution of nanoparticle size obtained by SP-ICP-
746 MS; (b) Histogram showing the distribution of nanoparticle sizes obtained by TEM; (c)
747 Micrograph of AgNPs obtained by TEM. Scale bar: 50 nm.

748 Fig. 2. Spore viability of *Fusarium* species on Maize-Based Medium (MBM) after different
749 AgNP treatments. Error bars represent standard deviations.

750 Fig. 3. Lag periods in colonies of *Fusarium* species on MBM after different AgNP
751 treatments. Standard deviations ranged 0–5 hours. Error bars are not shown because of
752 poor visibility.

753 Fig. 4. Radial growth rates of *Fusarium* spp. colonies on MBM after different AgNP
754 treatments. Error bars represent standard deviations.

755 Fig. 5. Accumulation of DON, 3-AcDON and ZEA by *F. graminearum* and *F. culmorum* in
756 MBM cultures after different AgNP treatments. Incubation time: 10 days. Incubation
757 temperature: 28 °C. Error bars represent standard deviations.

758 Fig. 6. Accumulation of T-2 and HT-2 toxins (*F. sporotrichioides* and *F. langsethiae*) and
759 NIV (*F. poae*) in MBM cultures after different AgNP treatments. Incubation time: 10 days.
760 Incubation temperature: 28 °C, except in *F. langsethiae* cultures (25 °C). Error bars
761 represent standard deviations.

762 Fig. 7. Accumulation of fumonisin B1 and B2 by *F. proliferatum* and *F. verticillioides* in
763 MBM cultures after different AgNP treatments. Incubation time: 10 days. Incubation
764 temperature: 28 °C. Error bars represent standard deviations.

765

Table 1

ED₅₀^a, ED₉₀^b and ED₁₀₀^c of AgNPs (µg/mL spore suspension) against spores of phytopathogenic or toxigenic *Fusarium* spp. at different exposure times. Evaluation of viable spores after treatments was carried out by monitoring the number of CFU/mL in MBM. Incubation temperature: 28 °C, except for *F. langsethiae* (25 °C).

Fungal species	Contact time AgNPs-fungal spores											
	2 h			4 h			20 h			30 h		
	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀
<i>F. graminearum</i>	14.2	40.8	45	6.4	9.3	10	2.3	7.7	10	1.0	1.8	2
<i>F. culmorum</i>	18.7	>45	>45	9.8	>45	>45	3.0	10.1	15	1.9	8.5	15
<i>F. sporotrichoides</i>	12.2	14.4	15	10.0	14.0	15	7.7	13.8	15	5.6	9.1	10
<i>F. langsethiae</i>	23.2	>45	>45	11.2	14.2	15	1.0	1.8	2	1.0	1.8	2
<i>F. poae</i>	7.2	9.4	10	6.3	8.6	10	5.4	9.1	10	1.0	1.8	2
<i>F. oxysporum</i>	17	42.1	>45	12.7	44.8	>45	12.2	31.7	45	4.7	17.7	45
<i>F. proliferatum</i>	22.3	>45	>45	11.7	42.5	>45	3.4	16.9	30	1.7	10.0	30
<i>F. verticillioides</i>	24.8	>45	>45	11.9	43.3	>45	3.3	19.0	30	1.7	10.5	30

a, b, and c: AgNP dose required to reduce the number of viable spores by 50%, 90%, and 100% compared to untreated controls under identical conditions.

Table 2

Arrangement of homogeneous groups within AgNP dose, *Fusarium* species and exposure time, with regard to their effects on spore viability, lag phase and growth rate in MBM cultures according to Duncan's multiple comparison procedure ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Factor	Level	Homogeneous groups								
		Spore viability			Lag phase			Growth rate		
		High	→	Low	High	→	Low	High	→	Low
AgNP dose ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0	•						•	•	
	2		•					•	•	
	5			•				•	•	
	10				•		•		•	
	15					•			•	
	30						•			•
	45					•	•			•
<i>Fusarium</i> spp.	<i>F. graminearum</i>			•			•			•
	<i>F. culmorum</i>		•					•	•	•
	<i>F. sporotrichioides</i>		•				•	•		•
	<i>F. langsethiae</i>			•			•			•
	<i>F. poae</i>			•			•			•
	<i>F. oxysporum</i>	•						•	•	•
	<i>F. proliferatum</i>		•						•	•
	<i>F. verticillioides</i>		•						•	•
Exposure time (h)	2	•						•	•	
	4		•						•	
	20			•			•			•
	30				•		•			•

Within each column, the levels containing a black circle form a group of means within which there are no statistically significant differences. Black circles in the same row indicate overlapping.

Table 3

Effective doses (ED₅₀^a, ED₉₀^b and ED₁₀₀^c) of AgNPs (µg/mL) in treatments of phytopathogenic or toxigenic *Fusarium* species able to reduce/inhibit colony growth on MBM cultures. Incubation temperature: 28 °C, except for *F. langsethiae* (25 °C).

Fungal species	Contact time AgNPs-fungal spores											
	2 h			4 h			20 h			30 h		
	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀
<i>F. graminearum</i>	35.2	43	45	6.8	9.3	10	7.3	9.5	10	1.0	1.8	2.0
<i>F. culmorum</i>	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	11.3	14.3	15	10.5	14.1	15
<i>F. sporotrichioides</i>	12.1	13.8	15	12.1	14.4	15	12.4	14.5	15	6.9	9.4	10
<i>F. langsethiae</i>	>45	>45	>45	11.2	14.2	15	1.0	1.8	2.0	1.0	1.8	2.0
<i>F. poae</i>	7.1	9.4	10	7.5	9.5	10	7.4	9.5	10	1.0	1.8	2.0
<i>F. oxysporum</i>	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	34.6	42.9	45	32.7	42.9	45
<i>F. proliferatum</i>	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	22.7	28.5	30	20.9	28.2	30
<i>F. verticillioides</i>	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	22.6	28.5	30	19.4	27.9	30

a, b and c: AgNP dose required to reduce colony radial growth rate by 50%, 90% and 100% compared to untreated controls under identical conditions.

Table 4

Table 4

Arrangement of homogeneous groups within AgNP dose, exposure time and *Fusarium* species with regard to their effects on mycotoxin accumulation in MBM cultures of various *Fusarium* species according to Duncan's multiple comparison procedure ($\alpha = 0.05$).

		Homogeneous groups							
		<i>F. graminearum</i> and <i>F. culmorum</i>			<i>F. sporotrichioides</i> and <i>F. langsethiae</i>		<i>F. poae</i>	<i>F. proliferatum</i> and <i>F. verticillioides</i>	
		DON ^a	3-AcDON ^b	ZEA ^b	T-2 ^b	HT-2 ^b	NIV	FB ₁ ^b	FB ₂ ^b
Factor	Level	High → Low	High → Low	High → Low	High → Low	High → Low	High → Low	High → Low	High → Low
AgNP dose (µg/mL)	0	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
	2		•		•	•	•	•	•
	5	• •	• •	•	•	•	•	•	•
	10	• •	• •	•	•	•	•	• •	• •
	15		• •	• •	•	•	•	•	•
	30		• •	•	•	•	•	•	•
	45		•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Exposure time (h)	2	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
	4	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
	20	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
	30	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Fusarium</i> species	<i>F. graminearum</i>	•	•	•					
	<i>F. culmorum</i>	•	•	•					
	<i>F. sporotrichioides</i>				•	•			
	<i>F. langsethiae</i>				•	•			
	<i>F. poae</i>						•		
	<i>F. proliferatum</i>							•	•
	<i>F. verticillioides</i>							•	•

Within each column, the levels containing a black circle form a group of means within which there are no statistically significant differences. Black circles in the same row indicate overlapping between groups.

^a There were not significant differences between the two species regarding mycotoxin accumulation.

^b There were significant differences between the two species regarding mycotoxin accumulation.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

